

Udiroko Religio-Cultural Festival in Ado-Ekiti

By Olusegun Olawoyin, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

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Udiroko is a renowned cultural festival in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. It began about 800 years ago as an occasion for the military chief of Ewi (the King of Ado-Ekiti) to give reports of their military campaigns in the preceding year and to pledge their continued loyalty to him. The festival also acts as the beginning of the new year for Ado-Ewi's indigenes. Since then, it has developed into sophisticated annual rituals and performances where Ado-Ekiti culture, particularly the royalty of the king, Ewi, is displayed. The cultural festival is usually celebrated in August of every year. It is marked at the time of the New Yam harvest in the city. Before this celebration, no one is permitted to eat of the yams harvested that season/year. This festival is of a high significance to the people of Ado-Ekiti as it relates to their ancestry, their identity and their cosmic space. It is centred around the king of the city. It is a ceremony which marks his spiritual authority and civil powers over his domain and people. He offers prayers to the high god as well as the ancestors who are believed to possess all the powers and wherewithal to keep the city safe, flourishing and prosperous as well as maintain the balance the city requires to blossom. The supernatural forces the king calls upon during the ritual are equally held as powerful as they have been acknowledged as the forces that keep the city from evil.

Date Range: 1300 CE - 2025 CE

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Southwest Nigeria, Ekiti

Ado-Ekiti is the capital of Ekiti State, Nigeria. Approximately, it sits at latitudes 7°35' to 7°39' North of the Equator and longitudes 5°10' to 5°19' East of the Greenwich Meridian.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

— No

Notes: But the cultural festival is not a closed event; it takes place in the palace.

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting?

– Yes

Notes: It takes place within the palace.

↳ Underground?

– No

Notes: It takes place on the palace ground.

↳ Is there an acknowledgment or reference to the elements or materials from which the setting is created? (e.g., wood or stone for a building)

– Yes

Notes: Yes, because it is the home of the revered king, the Ewi of Ado-Ekiti.

Is the ritual carried out in a public place?

– Yes

Notes: It is carried out in the palace.

↳ Is the public space restricted in any way? (i.e. public, but only for specific members of the religious group?)

– No

Is the ritual carried out in a private place?

– No

Notes: The city/town is owned by the people, so it cannot be called a private place.

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The palace of the King, Ewi.

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

– Yes

Notes: It is considered sacred because it is the abode of every Ewi for about eight centuries.

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

– Yes

Notes: The Udiroko takes place in the palace of the Ewi, the king of Ado-Ekiti.

↳ Was it temporary?

– No

↳ Was it permanent?

– Yes

Notes: It is the place every Ewi (king) of Ado-Ekiti lives. The palace can only be renovated; the ceremony cannot be moved to another venue.

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

– No

Notes: It was established.

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

– Yes

Notes: The palace is associated with the powerful effect of Ewi's prayers for all indigenes and residents of Ado-Ekiti at the conclusion of the festival.

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

– Yes

Notes: The crowns of the Ewi are always associated with the palace. The concentration of the traditional military chiefs to report their activities to the Ewi and the renewal of their oath of allegiance are also associated with the Aafin (palace).

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

– No

Notes: These natural features are not considered in the festival.

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

– No

Notes: The site has been established for centuries without taking this into consideration.

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

– No

Notes: It is within the palace (the Aafin).

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

– Yes

Notes: It takes place in August of every year.

↳ Annually:

– Yes

Notes: It takes place every August.

↳ Daily:

– No

↳ Weekly:

– No

↳ Seasonally:

– No

Notes: Except if we want to consider the fact that August, when the festival takes place, is considered the beginning of the new year for the people of Ado-Ekiti.

↳ Once in an individual's lifetime:

– No

Notes: It is annual, every year.

↳ Special events/occasions:

– No

↳ During life cycle events (marriage, birth, death, etc.):

– No

↳ Ad hoc:

– No

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified?

– No

Notes: It is specified.

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours)

– Yes: 72

Notes: The real festival takes place on a Saturday. However, there will be a Jum'at prayer in the mosque on Friday and a thanksgiving service in church on Sunday. This is to acknowledge the influence of Islam and Christianity in the ancient town of Ado-Ekiti.

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual?

def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual

– Yes

Notes: Members must have either their expertise or social connections to contribute to the success of the festival.

↳ How many agents are involved in this ritual?

– Yes: 15

Notes: Every Ado chief and principal indigene of Ado Ekiti is involved. However, the Udiroko Committee members are typically around 15.

↳ Are agents of specific gender/sex for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Both males and females are involved.

↳ What is the age range of agents in this ritual?

– Specify: 40-70

Notes: Usually, it is people of experience and energy.

↳ Do agents have to have biological distinctiveness for this ritual?

(e.g., twin, born breach, albino, mental illness, hermaphrodite, blind, other disability)

– Yes

Notes: Committee members must be indigenous to Ado-Ekiti.

↳ Do agents have to have a specific social role for this ritual?

(e.g., widow, unmarried, etc.)

– Yes

Notes: Among the committee members are chosen the chairman, secretary, treasurer, financial secretary, assistant secretary and technical adviser. Others are simply members

↳ Are agents required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are agents initiated?

– No

Notes: They are only inaugurated by the traditional council headed by the Ewi (king) of Ado-Ekiti.

↳ Are agents part of the social group?

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Are agents required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are agents required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are agents non-specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: But they have been involved in the cultural festival many times.

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for agents in this ritual?

(e.g., menstruating women, men of a certain age)

– Marriage status: No

– Age: No

– Gender: No

– Social caste: No

– Religious affiliation or status: No

– Physical state (e.g. menstruation, illness): No

Notes: Everybody is welcome.

↳ Are there supernatural agents associated with this ritual?

– No

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

– No

Notes: Indeed, should anybody be sick, there are medical personnel ready to treat them.

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

Notes: Revered ancestors like past monarchs are believed to be concerned about the going on in the city of Ado-Ekiti. They are interested in the progress of the city.

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: They are in the thousands, as many as can come, including non-indigenous people.

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:

– No

Notes: There is no sex/gender discrimination for participants.

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: Anybody can participate.

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Some do, while others do not. The different groups of Ado-Ekiti indigenes can also come forward to pledge their allegiance to the monarch. Participants can also come forward to contribute one developmental issue or another to the city.

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Both indigenes and non-indigenes are invited and can participate.

↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: All are welcome.

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

Notes: To bless and protect the city and the reigning monarch, the monarch's ancestors are expected to be present.

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Specifically, deceased kings from the inception of the city.

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

Notes: Except when the Muslim and Christian clergies pray for the presence of 'angels'.

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

Notes: Although the ancestors are dead, they are still 'living'.

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings

– No

Notes: Except if the ancestors are regarded as 'spiritual'.

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– No

↳ Others:

– Field Doesn't Know

Are there spectators in this ritual?

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

– Yes

Notes: In person, online, on television, etc., as many as can watch the event are welcome.

↳ How many spectators observe this ritual?

– I Don't Know

Notes: The numbers are not specified. As many as can enter the palace. But the programme is also relayed on television.

↳ The spectators' gender/sex is:

– Yes

Notes: Both male and female gender can watch the event.

↳ Male:

– Yes

↳ Female:

– Yes

↳ Transgender:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Non-binary:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ What is the age range of spectators in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: There is no age range.

↳ Do spectators have a specific social role for this ritual?

– No

Notes: They can only join in greeting the king, Kabiyesi.

↳ Are spectators required to be insiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Even non-Yoruba can watch the event. Indeed, indigenes invite their friends to come and watch the event.

↳ Are spectators required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are spectators required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are spectators non-specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The planners cannot even know ahead of time the nature of the spectators.

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for spectators to take part in this ritual?

– No

Notes: If a spectator will be present in the live programme, he or she should not be troublesome. And there are official security personnel watching over the attendees.

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as spectators in this ritual?

– No

Notes: Except the ancestors.

Cause/Trigger

Is this ritual practiced at will?

– Yes

↳ Is it individually determined:

– No

Notes: But the monarch, the Ewi, is the principal individual.

↳ Is it communally determined:

– Yes [specify]: The chosen planning committee.

Notes: In fact, the planning committee does everything at the instance of the monarch; the chiefs and other principal persons usually plan the event.

Is participation obligatory?

– No

Notes: Except for an individual who is a chief of Ado-Ekiti, then it is obligatory for such.

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

– Yes

Notes: It is the end of a year and the beginning of another for Ado-Ekiti.

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

– Yes

Notes: It is the beginning of a new year for the people.

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

– No

Notes: Except that the weather will be studied.

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

– Yes

Notes: New yam is also ushered in at this time. Before that, nobody is allowed to sell new yams in the city of Ado-Ekiti until Undiroro is celebrated.

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The festival is held during the rainy season.

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

– No

Notes: It is an annual event.

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

– No

Notes: It is a joyous celebration.

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

– No

Notes: It is an annual event.

Is this ritual part of another ritual?

– No

Notes: Although it is not part of another event, it is comprehensive in its purpose.

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants?

– No

Notes: The event is sponsored by the wealthy people of Ado-Ekiti. Well-wishers can also congratulate Kabiyesi/Oba (king) in the programme of events for a fee, which will be used to sponsor the event.

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: For 'maintenance' of the city. In the monarch's address, he is expected to report on happenings in the past year and to present a plan for the incoming year. The following day, the chiefs will meet again in the palace to review the king's address and to make further suggestions.

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change?

– No

Notes: But to cause further development of the city of Ado-Ekiti.

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it divine/spiritual:

– Yes

Notes: The purpose of the ritual is partly spiritual/divine. It serves to draw the ancestors, especially the spirits of all past kings of the city to issues of development and peace within the borders of the city.

↳ Is it non-human organic entities (e.g., nature, animals, plants):

– No

↳ Is it abiotic/inorganic entities (and objects):

– No

↳ Is it ecological:

– No

↳ Is it transformed humans:

– Yes

Notes: It serves to maintain a cordial relationship between the living members of the city and the past ancestors whose spirits are believed to be in touch with the city and are in control of all happenings therein.

↳ Is it for knowledge transmission (e.g., oral storytelling):

– Yes

Notes: The ceremony serves the purpose of oral storytelling such that some vital information about the city and its past are told during the annual rituals.

↳ Other:

– N/A

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– No

Notes: Except for the devotion to be proud of the culture and to contribute to the development of the city.

↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Not 'creation' of a culture per se, but the maintenance of culture.

↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is domestication of agents a goal?

Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: 'Cosmic' maintenance of Ado-Ekiti.

↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural agents?

– Yes

Notes: A purpose of the event is to express gratitude to God for all the good things he has done for Ado-Ekiti.

↳ Is this ritual performed for purification?

– No

Notes: It is more of an appreciation, but also to solicit God's further support for the city.

↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information?

– Yes

Notes: The reports of the chiefs and that of Ewi transmit information.

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)?

– Yes

Notes: By 'luck' is not meant 'chance', but progress.

↳ Is this a naming ritual?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence?

– Yes

↳ To increase the amount of rain for agricultural/horticultural productivity:

– No

Notes: Except it has not rained so much in the year of celebration.

↳ For crop success:

– No

Notes: In fact, the arrival of new yams will be celebrated during the event.

↳ For livestock success:

– No

↳ For success in gathering:

– No

Notes: Ado-Ekiti is a metropolitan city.

↳ For success in fishing:

– No

↳ For success in hunting:

– No

↳ For industrial productivity:

– Yes

Notes: By industrial productivity, I mean the general development of the town.

↳ For success in commerce/mercantilism/market exchange:

– Yes

Notes: Because Ado is a metropolitan centre.

↳ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes?

– Yes

Notes: The prayers will be said as the concluding part of Ewi's report. And because people believe that Ewi's blessings are effective, they believe it.

- ↳ Against spells/witchcraft:
 - Yes
 - Notes: For Ado-Ekiti indigenes and settlers.

- ↳ To avoid illness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: For Ado-Ekiti indigenes and settlers.

- ↳ To avoid injury:
 - Yes
 - Notes: For Ado-Ekiti indigenes and settlers.

- ↳ For a safe pregnancy:
 - Yes
 - Notes: For Ado-Ekiti indigenes and settlers.

- ↳ For children:
 - Yes
 - Notes: For Ado-Ekiti indigenes and settlers.

- ↳ To avoid discovery:
 - No

- ↳ Against weapons:
 - Yes
 - Notes: For Ado-Ekiti indigenes and settlers.

- ↳ To avoid vices (temptation):
 - Yes
 - Notes: For Ado-Ekiti indigenes and settlers.

↳ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)?

– Yes

Notes: This is the origin, when Ewi's military chiefs had to come to give reports of their campaigns in the previous year and renew their oath of allegiance.

↳ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with infanticide?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with travel?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations?

– Yes

Notes: As stated above, the prayers are giving the concluding part of Ewi's address.

↳ As part of a celebration:

– Yes

Notes: New year celebration.

↳ For love:

– Yes

Notes: Love among the Ado-Ekiti people.

↳ For social coordination:

– Yes

Notes: For the peace and progress in Ado-Ekiti principally, but even for Nigeria at large.

↳ To reduce social discord:

– Yes

Notes: To reduce social discord, especially in Nigeria.

↳ To maintain partner faithfulness:

– No

↳ To cause religious conversion:

– No

↳ To obtain subjugation/control:

– No

Notes: During the precolonial era, the prayers may have been for the subjugation of territories, but this is no longer the case.

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success?

– No

Notes: For an individual, no; for the city, Ekiti State and Nigeria, yes.

Is the causal efficacy assessed?

– No

Notes: It is strongly believed that Ewi's blessings and prayers are effective. This is corroborated by the aphorism, "Oun to Ewi aye ba wi ni Orun n gba" (whatever Ewi said on earth is always sanctioned in heaven).

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Drums, songs and dances are performed.

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community?

– Yes

Notes: It is explicitly called music.

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

– Yes

↳ Is it oral?

– Yes

Notes: Singing accompanies the sounds.

↳ Is it communal? (e.g., choir)

– Yes

Notes: The Olori and different groups play music together, involving instruments and songs.

↳ Is it individual?

– No

↳ Is there a call and response?

– Yes

Notes: Although call and response make up a small percentage of the performances, it is always available.

↳ It involves singing:

– Yes

Notes: All the songs in Ado-Ewi dialect of Ekiti, singing praises of God, the monarch's ancestors and the current monarch.

↳ It involves chanting:

– Yes

Notes: The praise song of the monarch is always sung.

↳ it involves invocation/prayer:

– Yes

Notes: The monarch always says prayers at the end of his report.

↳ It involves mantras:

– No

↳ It involves wailing/cheering (heightened emotional expression):

– Yes

Notes: When the monarch and the military chiefs arrive at the venue, there is cheering. During the speeches, there is cheering.

↳ It involves narrative/recitation:

– Yes

Notes: The achievements of the ancestors of the monarch are sometimes recited in songs or chants.

↳ It involves whistling:

– No

↳ It involves shouting/loud vocalizations:

– Yes

↳ How many individuals are involved in creating the vocalizations?

– Yes

Notes: As many as know what to vocalise at a particular time.

↳ Is the sound scripted?

– No

↳ Is the sound semantic?

– Yes

↳ How many languages are used in the ritual?

– Specify: 1

Notes: The Ado-Ewi Ekiti dialect.

↳ Which language(s) are used in the ritual?

– Specify: Yoruba (Ekiti)

Notes: In fact, the Ado-Ewi dialect of Ekiti.

↳ Is the language(s) confined to the ritual:

– No

Notes: It is the indigenous language of Ado-Ekiti.

↳ Is it esoteric ritual language:

– No

↳ Is it esoteric divine language (i.e., speaking in tongues):

– No

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– No

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– No

Notes: The language is spoken anywhere in Ado-Ekiti at all times.

↳ Is it specifically carried out by ritual specialists?

– No

↳ Does it require formal training?

– No

Notes: Indigenes and residents learn the language by hearing and practising speaking it.

↳ Do the vocalizations change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The particular event being done and what a speaker says determine this.

↳ Is the change in vocalization correlated to the stage(s) of the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is there musical texture in the loud vocalizations?

– Yes

↳ Is it homophonic:

– Yes

Notes: Participants, starting from the wives of the monarch (the Oloris), the military and other chiefs, and other dignitaries and other citizens, present.

↳ Is it monophonic:

– No

↳ Is it polyphonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it heterophonic:

– No

↳ Is it biphonic:

– No

↳ Are the vocalizations regulated by pitch?

– Yes

Notes: The fact that the language is tonal and they are songs makes pitch involved.

↳ Are they codified?

– Yes

↳ Are the vocalizations regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Do they have a pulse?

– Yes

Notes: Because they are songs,

↳ Do they involve codified patterns?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– N/A

Notes: The researcher is not aware of this.

↳ Are the vocalizations considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: They are part of the celebration.

↳ The sound is:

–Other: Both fixed and improvised, because, in call and response, the solo may improvise, but the chorus is fixed.

↳ Is the sound produced with parts of the body?

– Yes

↳ Does the sound involve hand movement?

– Yes

Notes: Dancing is also very much performed.

↳ Does it involve clapping?

– Yes

Notes: The clapping is also rhythmic.

↳ Does it involve body concussion?

– I Don't Know

↳ Does the sound involve feet movement?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing the sound:

– Field Doesn't Know

Notes: Many people, sometimes the whole participants are involved.

↳ Is the sound/movement scripted?

– No

↳ Is the sounds/movement semantic?

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes they are used to communicate in songs.

↳ Is the sounds/movement mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– No

↳ Is this sound/movement restricted to ritual use?

– No

Notes: It is used at all times.

↳ Is the sound/movement carried out by specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes the individuals singing the songs could be termed as specialists but may not always be classified as professional artists.

↳ Does it require formal training?

– No

↳ Does the sound/movement change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is the change correlated to the stage of the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the particular item.

↳ Is there musical texture in the sound?

– Yes

↳ Is it homophonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it monophonic:

– No

Notes: Except during call and response.

↳ Is it polyphonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it heterophonic:

– No

↳ Is it biphonic:

– No

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?

– Yes

Notes: As Yoruba songs, they are tonal.

↳ Is it codified?

– No

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Is there a pulse?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve codified patterns?

– No

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Especially the chanting and forms of greeting the Ewi.

↳ The sound is:

– Other: Both fixed and improvised.

↳ Does the sound involve conscious agency?

– Yes

↳ Are there instruments/objects involved in creating sounds for the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they membranophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating a membrane (e.g., kettle drums, cylindrical drums).

– Yes

Notes: The Olori's Agere, is a membranophone. Others are also there.

↳ Are they idiophone:

Definition: Instruments that create sound through vibrating themselves (e.g., xylophones, jaw's harp).

– Yes

↳ Are they aerophone:

Definition: Instruments that create noise by pushing vibrating columns of air through them (e.g., accordions, pitch pipes, ocarinas, bagpipes).

– No

↳ Are they chordophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating strings (e.g., guitar, violin, harp).

– No

↳ Are they electrophone:

Definition: Instruments where the sound is produced by electric or electronic means (e.g., synthesizers, computers).

– No

↳ Are they architectural features:

def: water channeled in underground canals, fountains, or other architectural features that create sounds for the ritual

– No

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing these instrumental sounds:

– Field Doesn't Know

Notes: Many people can be involved at a time.

↳ Is it scripted?

– No

↳ Is it semantic?

– Yes

Notes: Several times the performers are communicating meaning.

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– No

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– No

↳ Is it performed by specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Traditional performers of the sounds.

↳ Does it require formal training?

– Yes

Notes: There are families that it is their professional work.

↳ Does the sound change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the song being sung.

↳ Does the change correlate to the stage of the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is there musical texture in the instrumental sound?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve codified patterns?

– No

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Is there a pulse?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Codified/non-codified patterns

– No

Notes: They are non-codified patterns

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ The sound is:

– Other: Fixed and improvised.

Is movement involved in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The Oloris, the traditional police (Efas), and other groups dance.

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: It is explicitly called 'dance' or 'performance'.

↳ Is it coordinated with sound?

– Yes

Notes: The Olori, for example beat Agere, a long and big traditional drum, which are sometime carried on the head.

↳ Does it involve the use of objects?

– Yes

Notes: The drums, gongs, and other objects are involved.

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement

– N/A

Notes: Many people are usually involved; sometimes, the whole audience joins in the performance.

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The monarch usually dress gorgeously, and wears his beautiful crown. Other crowns are always displayed. Different groups, particularly the Oloris also dress gorgeously.

↳ Are there specific body markings done for the ritual?

– No

Notes: No body markings at all.

↳ Is there hair regulation as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is there tooth modification involved in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are individuals partly or fully naked as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: In fact, nakedness is forbidden.

↳ Are scars made as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Are piercings made as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Does genital modification take place during this ritual?

– No

↳ Do individuals have to wear specific clothing for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Except a particular group/society agrees to wear specific clothing for the occasion, and this is common.

↳ Are there jewelry/charms used during this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Charm is not used, jewelries are used as ornaments.

↳ Are masks used during the ritual?

– No

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: Except for the crowns that are displayed.

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals participate in consumption?

– N/A

Notes: As many as are interested.

↳ Is food consumed?

– Yes

↳ Is it human:

Definition: this can include by fire, natural features of landscape

– No

↳ Is it a non-human animal:

– Yes

↳ Is it a plant:

– Yes

Notes: Vegetables are part of the food.

↳ Is it a fungus:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Is this food restricted to the ritual?

– No

↳ Is the preparation of the food ritualized?

– No

↳ Is the presentation of the food ritualized?

– No

↳ In what state is the food consumed?

– Cooked

Notes: For joyous consumption.

↳ Is a non-normative portion (excessive or deficient) served?

– No

↳ Is it sacralized food?

– No

↳ Is it symbolic food?

e.g., standing in for another food or substance or metaphysical concept

– No

Notes: More of a Thanksgiving or celebration.

↳ Is the food consumed associated with healing powers?

– No

↳ Does food consumption happen on site?

– Yes

Notes: At the conclusion of the event, participants are served food.

↳ Does the food consumption happen off site?

– No

Notes: Except for the king, who must not be seen eating in public.

↳ Does the ritual take place before food consumption?

– Yes

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the supernatural source of the food?

– No

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the environmental source of the food?

– No

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the (human) provider of the food?

– No

↳ Does the ritual encourage sustainable eating behavior?

– No

↳ Are there specific types of consumption that are forbidden?

– No

↳ Is a psychoactive substance used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Just different types of alcoholic beverages (strong drinks) or wines.

↳ Is it a type of alcoholic drink?

– Yes

↳ Is it naturally fermented:

– Yes

Notes: The palm wine consumed during the ceremony are usually naturally fermented.

↳ Is it distilled:

– Yes

Notes: Other alcoholic beverages are usually distilled in manufacturing industries around the country while others may be imported

↳ Is it a stimulant?

– Yes

Notes: Just beer and other types of wine.

↳ Is it modern tobacco:

– No

↳ Is it pre-modern tobacco:

– No

↳ Is it caffeine:

– No

↳ Is it betel nut:

– No

↳ Is it khat:

– No

↳ Is it coca:

– No

↳ Does it contain cacao?

– No

↳ Does it contain kava?

– No

↳ Is it cannabis or cannabinoid?

– No

↳ Is it opium?

– No

↳ Is it MDMA?

– No

↳ Is it a psychedelic?

– No

↳ How is the substance used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The drinks are consumed

↳ Is it smoked:
– No

↳ Is it ingested:
– No

↳ Is it applied topically:
– No

↳ Is it chewed:
– No

↳ Is it a suppository:
– No

↳ Is it snorted:
– No

↳ Is it injected:
– No

↳ Is it offered into the fire:
– No

↳ Is it offered to non-human animals or natural features:
– No

↳ Does it require fasting beforehand:

– No

↳ Does it cause vomiting:

– No

↳ Are other substances used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Is the substance shared from a communal vessel or implement?

– Yes

Notes: Different groups may buy their own drinks.

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness?

– No

Notes: Just a celebratory mood.

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: Except for some individuals who want to contribute to the development of Ado Ekiti city.

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual?

– No

Notes: In contemporary times, Udiroko is primarily for celebration.

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself?

– Yes

Notes: It has been celebrated for about 800 years.

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals?

– No

Notes: It is celebrated alone.

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?

– I Don't Know

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?

– I Don't Know

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?

– Medium

Notes: The greetings of the Kabiyesi is repetitious.

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

– Medium

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

– High

Notes: Because raising the mood is common in the cultural festival.

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

– High

Notes: Dancing, movement, and other physical activities are common.

Is there behavioral conformity?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of behavioral conformity

– High

Notes: Whether in the cheering of the monarch or other activities, everyone wants to be in line.

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

– No

Notes: Every activity is done on stage.

Is there entrainment in this ritual?

– Field Doesn't Know

Is there coordination in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Except that the planning committee will make sure everything goes as planned.

↳ What is the level of coordination?

– High

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The planning committee of about 15 are always chosen to prepare. The Ewi himself may need to consecrate himself for the day.

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation?

– Specify: 2190

Notes: About three months, at least.

Are there preparation activities involved?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Particularly by the Ewi himself.

↳ Does it involve purification:

– Yes

Notes: Especially by the Ewi himself.

↳ Does it involve learning/training:

– No

↳ Does it involve penance:

– No

↳ Does it involve abstention:

– No

Notes: Not necessarily, except when the Ewi fasts.

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual?

– No

What is the level of expertise required?

– Low

Notes: None whatsoever.

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual?

– I Don't Know

Notes: I do not know the exact cost of hosting the event but it is sufficient to note that a very high cost is usually involved in celebrating Udiroko.

What is the transmission mode of the ritual?

- Exoteric

How is the ritual transmitted?

- In oral form
- Artistic representation
- Through social imitation

Notes: It is primarily transmitted through practice.

Who or what has authority over this ritual?

- Myth or legend
- Sagely human

Notes: The king, Ewi Ado-Ekiti, and the tradition of Ado-Ekiti are the powers behind the cultural festival

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